

Resource conflicts in the ecologically just city

Game materials

Role cards	DIN A4
Disruptive events	DIN A4
Dream Journey	DIN A4

Role card

RIVER

River and lifeline of the region

You are the _____, a majestic river that has made life possible in the region for thousands of years. You are proud of your role as a giver of life and home to countless organisms that live and thrive in and around your waters. But recently, you have felt a deep sense of worry and despair. You have struggled with low water levels almost every year. Lately you were dredged so that steamers could sail again. Now plans for a new chip factory are threatening your water level and thus your existence and that of your residents.

A separate water drainage system is being planned for the expansion of the chip industry, which will take up to 900 m³ of water every hour. This water will be used to cool the machines and 80% to 90% of it will be returned to you. When the machines are cooled, the water is heated, which means it is returned to you at a higher temperature than it was extracted. Water consumption in industry is set to double in a few years. In combination with dry summers due to climate change, you fear that you will not have enough water for life in and around you.

Thoughts and demands

You feel that you have been ignored by the planning to date and that your rights have not been sufficiently respected. You have the right to exist and flow in your natural state. Your well-being is inextricably linked to the well-being of the living beings in and around you. You are more than just a resource; you are a living ecosystem.

Goals in the stakeholder workshop

You, the Elbe, are fighting for more ecological justice and for your needs to be recognized. You want to emphasize how closely interwoven the world is and that all living beings should be respected. You contribute your emotions and legitimate demands to find sustainable solutions together with human and more-than-human stakeholders. Consider your value and demand your rights.

Role card

You are the soil - nothing here works without you!

You form the basis for all the visible diversity of life - that's why you are in close contact with flora and fauna and together you form an ecosystem.

One tablespoon of you contains one million bacteria, 120 thousand fungi and 25 thousand algae. Processes take place in you that provide the plants with vital nutrients and water supplies and you provide a habitat for various creatures. At the same time, these organisms enable you to survive. You are proud of this community!

But this coexistence is constantly being put to the test. Changes in the ecosystem affect you - and direct interventions in particular hurt you. That's why you're annoyed about the existing plans for an industrial water pipeline that will carry water from the river to the chip factories. For you, this means that heavy machinery is driving on top of you and squeezing you, causing you injuries by digging up or shooting through pipes for the pipeline. Among other things, the interventions change your pore systems and thus your ability to absorb and store oxygen and water. As a result, the perfectly harmonized processes are disrupted or even destroyed. This not only means changes for you, but also for your relationships, especially with flora and fauna!

Thoughts and demands

You have the right to exist in your natural state. Your well-being is inextricably linked to the well-being of the living beings in and around you. You are more than just a resource; you are a living ecosystem.

Goals in the stakeholder workshop

You, the soil, are fighting for more ecological justice and for your needs to be recognized. You want to emphasize how closely interwoven the world is and how all living beings should be respected and considered. You contribute your emotions and legitimate demands in order to find sustainable solutions together with human and more-than-human stakeholders. Consider your value and claim your rights.

Remember that an ecosystem is not only characterized by you as fauna, but also consider the interaction with flora and the soil. You are welcome to consult and support each other.

Role card

FLORA

You are the magnificent and diverse flora. In your world the heart of nature pulsates in every creature. You have knowledge of ecosystem that has been changing for centuries and you are right in the middle of it. As flora, you contain all the plant life of an ecosystem, from the largest tree to the partially hidden moss on the ground, forming a community of many different plant species. Due to your diverse vertical structures, you offer resources for many animals to live, for example fruits serve as food, tree hollows as breeding and living places – just think of the many insects you hear buzzing every day. The planned construction of an underground water pipeline across the ecosystem is the next project in the series of human uses that will affect you. The thought that the first trees could soon be felled in the areas where the pipeline is to run makes you feel sick. Without taking you into consideration, individuals are simply to be removed and your dispersal area reduced. In addition, the felled wood, your property, is to be used as people like it. Furthermore, injuries to other plant species are unavoidable during felling – for example, wounded trees are more susceptible to pathogens and/or pests. And yet you are already struggling with the effects of anthropogenic climate change.

Thoughts and demands

You feel ignored by the previous planning and that your rights have not been sufficiently respected. You want your needs as part of the ecosystem and your participation in decision-making to be respected. You have the right to exist in your natural state. Your well-being is inextricably linked to the well-being of the living beings in and around you. You are more than just a resource; you are part of a living ecosystem.

Goals in the stakeholder workshop

You, the soil, are fighting for more ecological justice and for your needs to be recognized. You want to emphasize how closely interwoven the world is and how all living beings should be respected and considered. You contribute your emotions and legitimate demands in order to find sustainable solutions together with human and more-than-human stakeholders. Consider your value and claim your rights.

Remember that an ecosystem is not only characterized by you as fauna, but also consider the interaction with flora and the soil. You are welcome to consult and support each other.

Role card

FAUNA

You are the fauna and in your world the heart of nature pulsates in every creature.

You have knowledge of the ecosystem, which has been undergoing changes for centuries and you are in the middle of it. As fauna, you represent the community of all animal species that can be found in the ecosystem. You are part of an ecosystem that is already under stress due to human utilization. Now the stress on the ecosystem is to be increased by the construction of an underground water pipeline. The construction of the water pipeline will affect you and your functions. Your habitats will be destroyed and your territories disrupted, especially by clearing a wide aisle. In addition, the construction noise is a major annoyance for you. You feel threatened by the idea of being exposed to such a danger and are annoyed by people's recklessness.

Thoughts and demands

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Goals in the stakeholder workshop

You, the fauna, are fighting for more ecological justice and for your needs to be recognized. You want to emphasize how closely interwoven the world is and how all living beings should be respected and considered. You contribute your emotions and legitimate demands in order to find sustainable solutions together with human and more-than-human stakeholders. Consider your value and claim your rights. Remember that an ecosystem is not only characterized by you as fauna, but also take into account the interaction with flora and the soil. You are welcome to consult and support each other.

Role card

COMPENSATION
AREA - LAKE _____

You are lake _____, a lake on the edge of the city _____. Although you were created artificially by flooding a former sand pit, you have developed into a near-natural biotope over the course of your life and provide a home for numerous organisms. You are proud of your water lilies, which serve as a habitat for dragonflies and amphibians, your reed beds, in which a wide variety of birds raise their young in spring, and your water bed, which is home to a multitude of microorganisms. You have every reason to be very satisfied with yourself and your many functions for the ecosystem. But you also know that your system can quickly tip over. Dying plant debris and sediment will cause sludge to accumulate over time. This sludge releases nutrients into your water and can lead to the mass proliferation of algae and bacteria, which deprive other living organisms of oxygen. The result is a loss of the diversity of organisms that you care so much about. In the past, you have already been dredged and desilted several times by humans and this is now urgently needed again. In the context of construction projects, it is a legal requirement that compensatory measures must be implemented when interfering with nature. Therefore, the impact caused by the construction of the water pipeline for the chip industry must also be compensated for. In the search for possible compensation areas, people have once again become aware of you. In addition to other measures, there is talk of desilting and renaturalizing you.

Thoughts and demands

You could benefit from the construction of the water pipeline. You realize that not only you, but also all the creatures that live in and around you could benefit from this. That is why you want to campaign for the water pipeline to be built. Although you do not want other more-than-human beings to suffer elsewhere, you want people to once again devote themselves to your needs. You therefore do not question which nature is generally worth protecting.

Goals in the stakeholder workshop

Since you want to support people in the construction of the water pipeline and can also speak from the perspective of a more-than-human system, you have the opportunity to act as a mediator between humans and more-than-human beings. You can do this by expressing both rational arguments and your feelings. Consider your value and demand your rights.

Role card

RESIDENT

You live in _____, love nature and spend a lot of time in your garden near the planned building project. You particularly enjoy your free time on long walks in the area, which has a deep emotional meaning for you. The tranquility and beauty of this landscape offer you a valuable retreat and contribute significantly to your well-being. On an excursion through the area, you learnt that this area has been heavily influenced by humans. It is now a protected area and home to many endangered species. However, you will also see the economic benefits of the project. Your partner, trained in the semiconductor industry and currently looking for a job, speculates on working for a Semiconductor Company. The opening of a new plant, which will create new business opportunities and strengthen the city as a technology center, is only possible by building its own water supply. This would not only provide jobs for your partner, but also for many other local residents, which could reduce the unemployment rate and increase the economic stability of the region. You also observe your children's interest in technological progress and hope for positive effects on education and research.

Thoughts and demands

You are a little ambivalent about the construction. On the one hand, you are happy about the opportunities for your partner and the city, but on the other hand you are worried about your beloved retreat and all the components of this ecosystem. With the next generations in mind, you also consider whether there is a risk that the intensive use of water resources by the chip industry is not sustainable in the long term and could pose problems for future generations.

Goals in the stakeholder workshop

As an affected resident, you want to emphasize in the discussion that both the ecological and economic impact of the construction must be carefully weighed up. It is important to you that the area is protected, while at the same time the economic benefits of the water pipeline construction are not disregarded. Only through a balanced dialogue between all parties involved can a sustainable and future-oriented decision can be made. Choose your own point of view.

Role card

ECONOMIC
DEVELOPMENT

You are employed by the city of _____ in the Economic Development Department.

Your area of responsibility includes creating and maintaining a diverse range of industries and the city's global competitiveness. The semiconductors manufactured in the chip factories are used in a wide variety of products. A single electric car, for example, contains up to 1,500 chips. The city's chip factories already form the largest microelectronics cluster in Europe. With the announcement that another factory is to be added to this cluster, this status can be further secured. You are aware of the enormous geopolitical potential of this expansion. You also see the expansion of the chip industry as a major advantage for the city. It is estimated that the industry will need thousands of new workers soon - this could mean more training centers, jobs and the construction of housing, kindergartens, schools and much more.

Thoughts and demands

You see the chip factory as an industry with a promising future that will create permanent jobs. The jobs will attract more skilled workers to the city, who will then need living space or places at educational institutions. You can see the potential here that investment in the housing market, educational facilities, etc. will not only make the city a more attractive place to work, but will also improve the cityscape - in short, the expansion of the chip industry is to the benefit all citizens. The construction of an independent water system is the first step in this direction.

Goals in the stakeholder workshop

You, a representative of the city's economic development department, are fighting for the construction of the water pipeline. In addition to the international economic benefits for the city, you also see the potential for the citizens, which an expansion of the chip industry would mean. With your professional but also emotional background, you argue in favor of the construction and try to achieve the best cost-benefit ratio in the discussion with the other stakeholders.

Role card

SEMICONDUCTOR
COMPANY

You are an ambassador for the semiconductor. You have already represented the interests of the world's largest semiconductor manufacturer on various continents. Now it's your job to oversee the opening of the next plant in _____. The city of _____ can benefit from the opening in various ways. On the one hand, your company is investing billions of euros in the construction and on the other, you want to create thousands of new jobs with the plant. This is not only to the benefit of the city - you are also giving many citizens the chance to take on a secure and well-paid job. Without the chips you produce, nothing will work today and especially in the future. They are needed for a wide variety of areas: Energy transition, artificial intelligence, 5G, digitalization and the automotive industry. For a single electric car, for example, up to 1,500 chips are needed. In 2022, the demand for chips could not be met, this can cause manufacturers to temporarily stop production. As a result, several thousand people are in danger to lose their jobs. In order to be able to cushion such economic crises, it is necessary to expand the chip industry in _____.

Thoughts and demands

You are convinced that the world needs chips - without chips from the semiconductor industry, there is no business for many companies. For these reasons, it is to everyone's advantage when the plant can open. Ultimately for you personally too, because success in this project will open further doors in your professional career. However, to cover the water consumption of the plant the separate industrial water pipeline is needed. The water pipeline is the first step in upgrading the city.

Goals in the stakeholder workshop

You, as a representative of a semiconductor company, are fighting for the water pipeline to be built as soon as possible so that the chip factory can be opened. In addition to the international economic benefits for your company, you also see the potential for the citizens that an expansion of the chip industry would mean. With your professional and emotional background, you argue in favor of the construction and try to achieve the best cost-benefit ratio in the discussion with the other stakeholders.

Disruptive Events

Disruptive events can create opportunities to enable participants to respond flexibly and creatively to unexpected challenges and consider the long-term consequences. The different events have different points in time for optimal use. When choosing to use one of the disruptive Events the discussion will be paused for the moderation to elaborate the scenario and guide the following steps.

The participants must now...

- Discuss the new research findings and assess their significance for the project.
- Review and adapt their previous plans and assumptions in order to minimize the ecological impact.
- Develop possible alternative measures to reduce the negative impacts.
- Consider whether additional protective measures or changes in project implementation are necessary.

The different events and their characteristics are described in the following.

1. Environmental disaster:

- **Description:** A sudden environmental emergency, such as a major flood or extremely low water, that affects water supplies and construction plans.
- **Aim:** Participants must react quickly to the new threat and adapt their plans.
- **Use case:** To be used when the discussion stagnates or when participants are too stuck in their existing assumptions. This forces them to react quickly and adapt their plans.

2. Public protest:

- **Description:** A citizens' movement launches protests against the expansion of the chip factory and demands more environmental protection.
- **Aim:** The participants must incorporate public pressure into their decision-making processes and possibly find compromises.
- **Use case:** To be used when the discussion stagnates or when the participants are too stuck in their existing assumptions. This forces them to react at short notice and adjust their plans.

3. Economic crisis:

- **Description:** An economic recession leads to budget cuts and changes the priorities of urban planning.
- **Aim:** The roles have to plan with scarcer resources and find new financing options.
- **Use case:** To be used when the financial aspects of planning are not sufficiently considered or to make participants aware of the complexity and uncertainty of long-term projects.

5. Scientific discovery:

- **Description:** New research results show unexpected ecological effects of the project.
- **Aim:** During the role play, participants are presented with a scientific report revealing that the planned expansion of the chip factory in the north of Dresden will lead to a significant decrease in groundwater levels in the Dresden Heath. This decrease in groundwater could:
 - Endanger the habitat for numerous plant and animal species.
 - Affect the health of the surrounding forests.
 - Have a negative impact on the drinking water supply of neighbouring communities.
- **Use case:** Use when participants seem confident in their decisions and new information may require a rethink. This encourages the questioning of existing assumptions and the integration of current scientific findings.

Dream Journey

You are invited to imagine what it is like to slip into a different role and take on a different perspective.

To do this, take a deep breath in and out, close your eyes and let the room slowly fade into the background. You will now spend a day in the body of your character, experience his or her world and experience what his or her everyday life in the city looks like.

It's morning, the day begins.

How does it feel to feel the first rays of sunshine? What sensations do you have when you perceive your surroundings? Are you outside or perhaps in an office?

What sounds do you hear? Are they the sounds of nature or perhaps the noise of the city? How do you feel about what the day has in store for you today? Are you in a good mood or are you perhaps worried?

It's midday and you explore your surroundings.

What challenges might you encounter? Are there any obstacles or dangers?

How do you interact with other creatures or elements around you? What relationships do you have with them?

What do you need to fulfill your needs? What resources do you use?

How much do you notice signs of change from human activities? Do they affect you more or less? How do you feel about this?

The day is drawing to a close. Evening is coming.

What changes do you notice in yourself and around you? Was it a positive or a stressful day? What significance does this day have for you? Are you worried about the future?

Whether the day ends here for you or you are active at night, you realize that you have received an invitation. The Dresden Urban Planning Office has written to you inviting you to take part in a stakeholder workshop. It's about the construction of the water pipes for the chip factory, which will also affect YOU. You are pleased about the invitation and that you can share your thoughts and feelings about the project. The night passes and the new day begins. The workshop is just around the corner.

You can now open your eyes again.

With that, I would like to welcome all participants of the stakeholder workshop...